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Tourism capacity and economic growth in selected African economies

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Abstract

The Vector Autoregressive approach is used in this study to investigate the capacity of tourism on the economic growth in selected African countries. (Nigeria, South Africa, Morocco, Mauritius, Kenya, Tanzania, and Tunisia) with panel analyses using data from 1995 to 2022. The variables for the study include gross domestic product (GDP) as a proxy for economic growth, tourism receipts (TR), and tourist arrivals (TAR). The result from the study shows that in the short-run tourism receipts was positive but non-significant on the economic growth of the countries, while it was positive and significant in the long run. Tourist arrivals were negative and non-significant in the short-run but positive and significant in the long-run. This shows that tourism has some positive impact on the economies of the selected countries and that their capacity for economic growth is significant. The study concludes that investment in the tourism industry should be adopted as a development strategy, given that tourism has the potential to improve economic growth.

Keywords: Tourism Capacity; African Countries; Vector error correction Model; Growth; JEL

1. Introduction

Tourism plays a vital role in the economic development of developing nations, emerging as a prominent revenue generator for both developed and developing nations (Costa, 2017). The potential for growth and development has been attributed to the expansion of tourism. Due to the significant multiplier effect it generates on various economic sectors, developing nations have implemented policies aimed at attracting tourists that typically exhibit a diverse range of preferences and requirements, encompassing various goods and services that include accommodation, transportation, and recreational activities (Okwo 2022). The goods and services in question are predominantly characterised by a high degree of labour intensity, making them a notable catalyst for the generation of employment opportunities; hence, it is unsurprising that the tourism sector serves as a significant source of employment, with the industry contributing up to 30 percent of global export services (International Labour Organisation (ILO), 2011). Tourism, being a labour-intensive sector, serves as a substantial provider of employment opportunities worldwide. It necessitates diverse skill sets and competencies while facilitating expedient entry into the workforce for individuals who frequently encounter challenges in securing employment, such as young individuals, women, and migrant workers.

Tourism is a multifaceted activity that encompasses multiple industries and relies on a diverse range of skills. Its advantages are distributed across a wider segment of society when matched with other sectors of the economic system (Telce & Schroenn, 2006). The cross-disciplinary nature of tourism contributes to its perceived potential for reducing inequality, leading to the emergence of the concept of "pro-poor tourism" as it ensures poverty reduction. Tourism plays a vital role in the economic development of numerous nations and has garnered significant scholarly attention. Though there is a limited body of research exploring the effect of tourism on promoting economic progress in nations with open economies, the progress of tourism has been found to have direct and indirect positive impacts across various sectors (Paramati, Alam, & Chen, 2017). Tourism has been recognised as a substantial catalyst for economic growth as it

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stimulates economic activities in the areas of origin, destination, and surrounding regions (Gavurova, Suhanyi & Rigelsky, 2020).

Grobler and Nicolaides (2016) studies shows that the tourism industry can cause irreversible environmental damage by putting pressure on fragile ecosystems, constructing resorts and roads that destroy natural sites, putting pressure on land, water, and air, and generating pollution, discharge of residuals, erosion, and deforestation. Despite the tourism sector making significant contributions to economic growth, Africa's tourism industry has not developed to the same extent as other worldwide regions. The governments of most African countries are not willing to invest in the tourism sector because it is capital-intensive and the return on investment is long-term.. The objective of the study is to determine the relationships between tourism and economic growth. considering tourism receipt, tourist arrivals. The hypotheses stated in the null that there is no significant of tourism receipt and tourist arrivals on the economic growth of the African countries selected.

2. Literature Review

Many studies support the idea that the tourist industry contributes to jobs and foreign exchange generation in addition to helping to generate household income. Consequently, it has been confirmed (Lee & Kwon, 1995; Lim, 1997) that a developed tourism industry contributes positively to economic progress in any given nation. Sub-Saharan Africa drew 33.1 million tourists in 2011 (UNWTO 2012), up from a small base of 6.7 million visitors in 1990. Tourism is a key sector pushing transformation in Africa.

2.1. Tourism and National Development

The tourism sector is one of the tools for sustainable development, as it generates jobs and stimulates the economies of nations in a variety of ways. It acts as one of the primary employers of labour and is a significant factor in most economies as it fosters growth in a variety of ways. Most African nations have included tourism in their national development objectives. The foundation for the growth of tourism has been established by promoting African nations as appealing travel destinations and cultivating skills related to tourism. The sector's capacity for diversification and the connections between equitable growth in the economy and tourism have received significant attention throughout Africa, UNCTAD (2017).

2.2. Tourism and Intersectoral linkages

The tourism industry recognises the importance of intersectoral linkages in contributing to sustainable development by creating jobs, promoting social inclusion, and protecting the environment. The sector has the potential to establish strong linkages with other sectors. Among the numerous types of industries, the tourism sector has significant intersectoral links and contributes to regional and national growth, as well as creating an additional industrial group. The tourism economy refers to the exchange of goods and services between tourists and the economy, along with different market segments such as ecotourism, cultural tourism, and medical tourism, to promote economic diversification.

2.3. Ecotourism

Ecotourism, which aims to save the environment and benefit local communities, is generally connected to remote areas. Ecotourism, as a dynamic subsector of tourism related to environmental conservation, has the capacity to contribute to long-term development and environmental sustainability. African economies have a competitive advantage in ecotourism due to their diverse natural landscapes, wildlife, and protected areas. Properly harnessing these advantages can promote economic diversification, job creation, and enterprise development while also addressing underdevelopment and environmental challenges in remote regions.

Durberry (2002) established that Mauritius's tourist industry is the main driver of economic growth. For the analysis, he used tests of causality and co-integration. Eugenio and Scarpa (2004) examined the nature of the connection between tourism and economic growth in Latin American nations between 1985 and 1998. Their findings demonstrated that while the tourism industry can support economic growth in low- and middle-income nations, it cannot do so in high-income nations.

Banday and Ismail (2017), tested the relationship between tourism revenue and economic growth in Brazil, Russia, Indian, China, and South Africa (BRICS) nations from 1995 to 2013 using the application of the Autoregressive Distributed lag co integration technique. The research supports the tourism-led growth hypothesis for the BRICS nations, revealing the beneficial impact of tourism on economic growth.

According to Payne and Mervar (2010), stable economic policies, sound governance practices, and investments in people and physical capital are what drive a nation's tourism industry. This upbeat and energetic atmosphere generates a number of development activities that multiply and enhance the tourism industry.

Okocha, Agina, and Ojiula (2021) conducted a study to assess the impact of tourism marketing on the development of Nigeria and other African nations. Their primary aim was to evaluate the effectiveness of marketing efforts in promoting Nigeria and other African countries as tourist destinations. The researchers collected secondary data and found that while some African countries are prioritizing tourism marketing, Nigeria's performance in this regard is lacking. This lack of commitment to tourism marketing has resulted in a decrease in international tourist arrivals and has had a negative impact on inbound receipts and GDP in Nigeria.

Antonakakis and Filis (2015) used a recently developed leakage index approach to examine the relationship between tourism and economic growth in Europe. The tourism-economic growth relationship is not stable over time in terms of magnitude and direction, according to the findings, which are based on monthly data for ten European countries from 1995 to 2012.

Santamaria and Filis (2019) examined the dynamic relationship between tourism development and anticipated macroeconomic conditions in an effort to significantly change the direction of studies in the tourism economics literature. The study examined the term structure of interest rates as a proxy for tourism development, while the number of foreign visitor arrivals was used as a measure of macroeconomic conditions instead of the current GDP level. Monthly statistics from January 1998 to June 2017 were analysed using a Dynamic Conditional Correlation (DCC-) GARCH model. The results showed a time-varying association between tourism growth and anticipated economic factors, which are influenced by cycle of business in addition to geopolitical and economic factors.

3. Methodology and Empirical findings

This study examined the relationship between tourism and economic growth by using the panel data from 1995 to 2022 for Nigeria, Tunisia Kenya, Tanzania, South Africa, Morocco, and Mauritius, adopting the vector autoregressive (VAR) technique. The variables for the study are tourism receipts (TR), tourist arrivals (TAR), exchange rate (EXR), foreign direct investment (FDI) and gross domestic product (GDP) (proxy for economic growth). These African countries are thought to have growing tourism economies, the data for the study were sourced from the World Bank.

The Harrod-Domar theory is the theoretical foundation for this study that explains how the amount of investment and saving determines an economy's growth rate. Finding the rate of income growth required to keep the economy running smoothly is of interest to Harrod and Domar.

The baseline model for this study follows the tourism-led growth model specified by Fayissa et al., (2007) and Dritsakis (2012) as shown in equation (1). The model states that an increase in tourism activities is associated with an increase in economic growth.

$$\ln GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln TR_t + \lambda \ln X_i + \varepsilon_t \dots (1)$$

Where $\ln GDP_t$

is the log of real GDP per capita, $\ln TR_t$ is the log of tourism receipts and $\ln X_i$ is the log of other relevant explanatory variables used in the study. To show the relationship between tourism on economic growth in the African countries The interactive term tourism arrival was introduced into the tourism-led growth model specified in equation(1).

$$\ln Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln TR * TART + \lambda \ln X_i + \varepsilon_t \dots (2)$$

Additional recognised determinants of economic growth variables, such as exchange rate ($\ln EXR_t$), foreign direct investment ($\ln FDI_t$), and terms of trade ($\ln TOT_t$), can be incorporated into the model in equation (2). These variables, which were modified from the baseline model of Fayissa et al. (2007) and Dritsakis (2012), are important factors that determine economic growth. The model for the study can be specify as follows:

$$\ln Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m \pi_1 \Delta Y_{it-1} + \sum_{i=0}^m \pi_2 \Delta TR_{it-1} + \sum_{i=0}^m \pi_3 \Delta TAR_{it-1} + \rho \ln Y_{it-1} + \rho \ln TR_{it-1} + \rho \ln TAR_{it-1} + \lambda ECM_{it-1} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

$$\dots(3)$$

where Δ is the first-difference operator, β_0 is intercept, t is time element, π_i represent the short-run parameters of the model, ρ_i are long-run coefficients, while ε_{it} is white noise error term and lastly, it represents country at a particular time and λ is the parameter of the error correction mechanism. The ECM_{it-1} represent a one lag error correction term that shows the speed of adjustment in the long-run.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics Result

	GDP	TR	TAR
Mean	111.8486	2.839235	4.092092
Median	47.19500	1.820000	2.760000
Maximum	574.1800	11.20000	15.12000
Minimum	4.040000	0.040000	0.290000
Std. Dev.	139.2893	2.912112	3.744140
Skewness	1.583655	1.492687	1.186108
Kurtosis	4.231723	3.952849	3.699569
Jarque-Bera	94.31675	80.19979	49.95390
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	21922.33	556.4900	802.0500
Sum Sq. Dev.	3783293.	1653.677	2733.625
Observations	196	196	196

Source: Authors Computation

The skewness values in Table 1 (i.e., 1.58 billion dollars for GDP of selected African countries, 1.49 billion dollars for tourism receipts (TR) of selected African countries, and 1.18 million persons for tourist arrivals (TAR) of the selected African countries) indicate that the distribution of these variables set has a long right tail with values greater than the sampled mean, while the kurtosis values (i.e., 4.23 billion dollars for GDP of selected African countries, 3.95 billion dollars for TR of selected African countries) indicate that these datasets were leptokurtic, producing higher values than the normal.

With their respective p-values of 0.00, 0.00, 0.00, 0.00, and 0.00 less than 0.05, the JB values of the gross domestic product (GDP) of selected African countries are 94.31 billion dollars; the tourism receipts (TR) of selected African countries is 80.19 billion dollars; and the tourist arrivals (TAR) of selected African countries is 49.95 million persons indicated that each variable's null hypothesis was rejected. Consequently, it indicated that the dataset did not follow a normal distribution. The test of multicollinearity was implemented using the correlation matrix to address this worry because the series were not normally distributed.

3.1. Test of multicollinearity: Correlation matrix

Table 2 presents the correlation matrix result of the study variables; The relationship between the gross domestic product (GDP) and tourist arrivals (TAR) of a subset of African countries was shown to have a positive and statistically significant correlation, with a p-value of 0.0000 and a correlation coefficient of 0.5298.

Table 2 Correlation Matrix

Covariance Analysis: Ordinary			
Correlation			
Probability			
Observations	GDP	TR	TAR
GDP	1.000000		

	196		
TR	0.375063	1.000000	
	0.0000	-----	
	196	196	
TAR	0.529870	0.860861	1.000000
	0.0000	0.0000	-----
	196	196	196

Source: Authors Computation

Also, with the correlation value of 0.8608 as well as a p-value of 0.0000, the association between the tourist arrivals (TAR) and tourism receipts (TR) of the African countries were found to be positive and significant.

Table 3 Result of panel unit root test (levels)

Variable	Common Unit Root				Individual Unit Root			
	Levin, Lin & Chin t*		ImPesaran and Shin W-stat		ADF - Fisher Chi-square		PP - Fisher Chi-square	
	Statistics	P	Statistics	P	Statistic	P	Statistic	P
GDP	2.6235	0.9956	3.9005	1.0000	3.4418	0.9980	4.6267	0.9904
TR	-2.1402	0.0162*	-0.8288	0.2036	14.832	0.3897	21.929	0.0801
TAR	-0.8083	0.2094	-0.6264	0.2655	15.245	0.3616	20.625	0.1116

Source: Authors Computation

Table 4 Result of panel unit root test (first difference)

Variable	Common Unit Root				Individual Unit Root			
	Levin, Lin & Chin t*		ImPesaran and Shin W-stat		ADF - Fisher Chi-square		PP - Fisher Chi-square	
	Statistics	P	Statistics	P	Statistic	P	Statistic	P
GDP	-4.7373	0.0000*	-5.6073	0.0000*	58.647	0.0000*	97.718	0.0000*
TR	-7.5652	0.0000*	-7.2920	0.0000*	76.476	0.0000*	127.15	0.0000*
TAR	-7.5742	0.0000*	-7.7526	0.0000*	78.950	0.0000*	130.31	0.0000*

Source: Authors Computation

3.2. Unit root tests

Table 4 shows that, with the exception of the PP-Fisher Chi-square method, none of the group's variables were shown to be jointly stationery at the 1 percent, 5 percent, and 10 percent significance levels. This is because the measurement value for each unit root in the data did not determine whether all of the variables were jointly integrated. Based on the results of the condensed group unit root tests at the appropriate significance levels, this investigation will accept the null hypothesis that the variables (TAR, GDP, and TR) have unit roots at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels.

3.2.1. Johansen cointegration test

Tables 3 and 4 show the results of the co-integration analysis based on the maximum eigenvalue statistic and the trace statistic utilizing the Johansen-Jesulius multivariate technique. The results from the multivariate cointegration analysis, which are presented in Table 5. provided at least one cointegrating equations for the trace statistic and also established one given a maximum eigenvalue statistic. Based on this finding, the study concluded that there was a long-term link between the variables because they were co-integrated.

Table 5 Vector error correction model (VECM) result

Vector Error Correction Estimates			
Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []			
Cointegrating Eq:	CointEq1		
LGDP(-1)	1.000000		
LTR(-1)	-37.51754		
	(14.6291)		
	[-2.56459]		
LTAR(-1)	-6.304824		
	(16.1787)		
	[-0.38970]		
C	23.61622		
Error Correction:	D(LGDP)	D(LTR)	D(LTAR)
CointEq1	0.000883	0.001663	0.001251
	(0.00040)	(0.00057)	(0.00051)
	[2.21253]	[2.93493]	[2.43615]
D(LGDP(-1))	-0.457634	0.008252	0.008216
	(0.07657)	(0.10870)	(0.09855)
	[-5.97684]	[0.07591]	[0.08337]
D(LGDP(-2))	-0.153634	0.036652	0.032734
	(0.07649)	(0.10859)	(0.09845)
	[-2.00850]	[0.33752]	[0.33250]
D(LTR(-1))	0.072933	-0.049034	0.143737
	(0.06115)	(0.08681)	(0.07870)
	[1.19272]	[-0.56486]	[1.82636]
D(LTR(-2))	0.064557	-0.174025	0.032859
	(0.06412)	(0.09102)	(0.08252)
	[1.00687]	[-1.91188]	[0.39818]

D(LTAR(-1))	-0.033746	0.018146	-0.356196
	(0.06783)	(0.09629)	(0.08730)
	[-0.49751]	[0.18844]	[-4.08011]
D(LTAR(-2))	-0.029490	0.071160	-0.158381
	(0.07188)	(0.10205)	(0.09252)
	[-0.41024]	[0.69730]	[-1.71187]
C	0.094713	0.044152	0.022487
	(0.01980)	(0.02810)	(0.02548)
	[4.78468]	[1.57113]	[0.88261]
R-squared	0.188477	0.076544	0.119786
Adj. R-squared	0.154461	0.037836	0.082891
Sum sq. resids	9.628052	19.40433	15.94913
S.E. equation	0.240110	0.340872	0.309037
F-statistic	5.540840	1.977480	3.246648
Log likelihood	5.444952	-55.87639	-38.71835
Akaike AIC	0.029201	0.730016	0.533924
Schwarz SC	0.173876	0.874692	0.678600
Mean dependent	0.060909	0.040870	0.022427
S.D. dependent	0.261122	0.347509	0.322701

Source: Authors Computation

Tourist arrivals (TAR) and tourism receipts (TR) from the chosen African nations did not increase GDP (gross domestic product, a measure of economic growth) in tandem, according to the VECM long term projections in Table 5 in relation to the stable coefficient of the VECM, the interactions between the tourist arrivals (TAR) and tourism receipts (TR) of the chosen African countries over time resulted in a 23.61 percent decline in GDP for the selected African countries. Additional analysis

$$GDP = -23.61 + 37.51 * TR + 6.30 * TAR \dots (4)$$

the long-run estimates in Equation 4 showed that, all other things being equal, the total value of tourism receipts (TR) of a subset of African countries will raise their GDP by 37.51% over time. This finding was determined to be statistically significant at the five percent significance level. Last but not least, the total value of tourist arrivals (TAR) of a subset of African countries will raise GDP levels in those countries by 6.30 percent over time. This relationship was found to be statistically non-significant at a five percent significance level, holding all other variables constant.

3.3. Decision Rule

Accept H_0 if the probability value is greater than five per cent (0.05) significance level.

Accept H_1 if the probability value is less than five per cent (0.05) significance level.

Table 6 VECM short run Wald test estimate with regards to relationship between tourism and economic growth

Test statistics	Chi-square value	D.F	Probability	Remarks
TR: C(4)+C(5)=0	2.1541	1	0.1422	Non-significant
TAR: C(6)+C(7)=0	0.3132	1	0.5757	Non-significant

Source: Authors Computation 2023

3.4. Test of hypothesis

Table 6 indicates that TR were statistically non-significant at the five percent significance level, as indicated by the TR value of 2.1541, which was paired with a probability value of $0.1422 > 0.0500$. Thus, it was determined that there is no meaningful correlation between tourism receipts as well as economic growth, accepting the study's null hypothesis.

It may be inferred from Table 6 that, at the five percent significance level, TAR was determined to be non-significant with a TAR value of 0.3132 and a value for probability ($0.5757 > 0.0500$). As a result, the study's null hypothesis—which held that there is no meaningful correlation between visitor arrivals and economic growth—was accepted.

4. Discussion of findings

The results demonstrated that, over the course of the study period, different tourism-related strategies had different effects on the rate of economic growth in a number of African countries, both in the short and long terms. The findings, as determined by VECM analysis, showed that, during short-run intervals, the arrival of tourists to the chosen African countries had a non-significant negative impact on the countries' economic growth but positive and significant in the long-run. Whereas tourism receipts of various lags were positive but not statistically significant on the economies of the selected countries but in the long-run tourism receipts had positive and statistically significant impact on the relevant economies. The result from the study also showed that exchange rate and foreign direct investment has positive and significant impact on the economies.

The study analysed results demonstrated that, over the course of the study period, different tourism-related strategies had different effects on the rate of economic growth in a number of African countries, both in the short-run and long run period. The findings, as determined by VECM analysis, showed that, during short-run intervals, the arrival of tourists to the chosen African countries had a non-significant negative impact on those countries' economic growth but positive and significant in the long-run. Whereas tourism receipts of various lags were positive but not statistically significant on the economies of the selected countries but in the long-run tourism receipts had positive and statistically significant impact on the relevant economies. The result from the study also showed that exchange rate and foreign direct investment has positive and significant impact on the economies.

5. Conclusion

Through reciprocal partnerships, tourism has mostly acted as an economic catalyst, promoting the growth of other businesses. The pace of increase in tourism offers several advantages to countries, including the capacity to address macroeconomic issues such as poverty, inflation, unemployment, and balance of payments imbalances.

The development of tourism depends on both public and private infrastructure since it draws tourists and foreign investment. Tourism has grown to be a substantial export sector in both rich and developing nations. The governments of African nations should take deliberate steps to attract foreign tourists, particularly with regard to foreign direct investments in tourism-related infrastructure. It is therefore recommended that governments and policymakers need to turn more attention to the sector's economic benefits and exploit the growth strategy in accordance with certain growth theory.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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